

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of L-cysteine and DL-methionine by morpholinium chlorochromate in aqueous acidic medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of the redox reaction of MCC (morpholinium chlorochromate) with L-cysteine and DL-methionine have been studied over the range $2.0 \leq 10^3 [\text{amino acid}]_T \leq 6.0$, $0.1 \leq [\text{H}^+] \leq 0.25$, $0.1 \leq I \leq 0.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $293 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 313 \text{ K}$ in aqueous perchlorate medium. The redox reaction showed first order dependence in $[\text{amino acid}]_T$ and $[\text{MCC}]_T$. The main products of the reaction were cystine and methionine sulfoxide respectively. The activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1}) and ΔS^\ddagger ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) for the redox reactions of L-cysteine and DL-methionine for k_1 and k_2 paths are found to be 44.82 ± 9.1 , 54.11 ± 7.1 , 26.69 ± 9.0 , 60.64 ± 12.24 and -243.05 ± 29.8 , -268.29 ± 23.4 and -206.62 ± 30.3 , -319.83 ± 40.43 respectively. The value of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were both favourable for electron transfer processes. Negative ΔS^\ddagger indicates the ordered transition state for the redox reactions.

Keywords : Kinetics and mechanism, morpholinium chlorochromate, L-cysteine, DL-methionine, redox reaction.

Introduction

Chlorochromates are mild selective oxidant and are used in synthesis of various organic compounds¹⁻⁵. These are used in some selective redox reactions. Oxidation of organic sulphides⁶, carbonyl compounds⁷, thioacids⁸, oxyacids of phosphorous⁹ and more recently redox reaction of alpha hydroxy acids like glycolic, lactic, malic and substituted mandelic acid by MCC¹⁰ have been reported. There are few reports on the redox reactions of sulfur containing amino acids by chlorochromates. The kinetics of oxidation of sulfur containing amino acids like cysteine and methionine by MCC in aqueous acidic medium is reported in this paper. Oxidation of methionine has received particular attention because of its biological interaction with several hormones¹¹. Cysteine and methionine are interesting bimolecules containing three coordination sites as O, N, S. It is interesting to know whether it binds chromium through O or N or S during electron transfer process. The products of the redox reactions have been isolated and characterized.

Experimental

Materials : MCC was prepared by reported method¹¹

and was characterized by analytical methods which are identical with reported data. L-Cysteine and DL-methionine (SRL, extra pure) were used as such without further purification. Ionic strength was maintained with KNO_3 . All other reagents used were of analaR grade. The solution was prepared in freshly prepared double distilled water using an all glass distillation apparatus containing KMnO_4 .

Kinetics :

The kinetics of oxidation of L-cysteine and DL-methionine by MCC were studied spectrophotometrically under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping the concentration of substrate at least ten times in excess over $[\text{MCC}]$, $[\text{substrate}]$ were varied from 2×10^{-3} to $6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ were varied from 0.1 to 0.25 mol dm^{-3} .

The decreased of absorbance with time was monitored at 425 nm (cysteine) and 350 nm (methionine). Kinetic measurement were carried out with Systronic 2202 UV-VIS spectrophotometer equipped with a thermostatic bath for temperature control. The rate constants (k_{obs}) were calculated from the slope of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ vs $t(\text{s})$ plots

from the relationship,

$$\ln |(A_t - A_\infty)| = \ln |(A_0 - A_\infty)| - k_{\text{obs}} \cdot t$$

where A_0 , A_t , A_∞ denote optical density of the reaction mixture at zero time, time t and infinite time respectively. A_∞ was measured after completion of the reaction. The correlation coefficients of plots used to determine k_{obs} were found to be 0.99 in most of the cases.

Stoichiometry and identification of products :

The reaction mixture containing substrate and MCC in ratio 1 : 10 (molar ratio) $I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3) were allowed to go to completion, the unreacted MCC, Cr^{VI} was estimated iodometrically¹². From the above stoichiometry study, it was found that the reaction exhibited a 3 : 1 stoichiometry for cysteine and 3 : 2 stoichiometry for methionine oxidation.

In order to get the reaction product 0.2 mol of MCC and 0.02 mol of amino acid (cysteine/methionine) were mixed separately in a container and $[\text{H}^+]$ was kept at $0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The reaction mixture were allowed to stand for about 2 h at 303 K for completion. It was kept in a refrigerator in a closed container for 24 h. The crystalline products were isolated and washed with diethyl ether.

The oxidation product of cysteine and methionine were separately dried in a desiccator. The yield of the products were nearly 70%. FTIR spectra of products were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer (UK) FTIR spectrometer. IR spectra of oxidation product of DL-methionine shows a characteristic sharp peak at nearly 1100 cm^{-1} is due to S=O stretching vibration¹³ and most of the peaks match with methionine sulfoxide. It can be inferred that the oxidation product of methionine is methionine sulfoxide. S-H stretching frequency at 2551 cm^{-1} in cysteine is absent in the oxidation product of cysteine suggesting that cysteine dimerises to cystine and most of the IR spectra of oxidation product of cysteine corresponds with that of cystine. It is concluded that oxidation product of methionine and cysteine are methionine sulfoxide and cystine respectively.

Results and discussion

The UV-VIS spectral scan of the reaction mixture of L-cysteine and DL-methionine with MCC were taken separately. The absorption maxima around 365 nm of MCC shifted to 425 nm for cysteine (Fig. 1a) and to 350 nm for methionine (Fig. 1c) respectively indicating the formation of an intermediate complex between amino acid with MCC. The intermediate complexes were unstable hence λ_{max} for the mixture decreased with increasing time for

Fig. 1(a,b). (a) UV-VIS spectral scan of L-cysteine with MCC, 30 °C, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (1) $[\text{MCC}] = 6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (2) $[\text{L-cysteine}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (3) immediate after mixing, (4) $\Delta t = 2 \text{ min}$, (5) $\Delta t = 5 \text{ min}$, (6)–(8) $\Delta t = 10 \text{ min}$; (b) inset after 24 h

Table-1 (contd.)

5.0	0.10	4.95	8.20	9.67	18.70	17.56
6.0	0.10	5.54	9.56	10.48	20.0	20.28
2.0	0.15	5.08	7.47	9.55	13.22	18.29
3.0	0.15	5.90	8.40	10.24	15.94	20.47
4.0	0.15	7.09	9.54	11.09	18.46	22.68
5.0	0.15	7.70	10.75	12.66	20.05	24.08
6.0	0.15	8.40	12.50	13.30	22.18	26.56
2.0	0.20	7.05	9.94	12.28	18.89	22.48
3.0	0.20	8.42	11.09	13.5	21.63	24.47
4.0	0.20	9.80	12.72	14.47	25.04	27.18
5.0	0.20	11.00	14.03	15.94	27.00	30.16
6.0	0.20	11.60	16.24	17.56	29.01	32.29
2.0	0.25	9.70	13.08	16.09	25.09	28.07
3.0	0.25	11.44	14.81	17.35	28.57	31.25
4.0	0.25	13.55	16.46	18.24	32.94	33.56
5.0	0.25	15.40	18.12	20.02	36.41	38.15
6.0	0.25	16.64	21.04	22.08	39.03	41.00

acid]_T. The same figure also indicates the increase of reaction rates with increase of [H⁺] where as *k*_{obs} was almost not affected by varying [MCC]. The observed rate of the reaction was studied by varying ionic strength *I* = 0.1 to 0.8 mol dm⁻³ at constant [MCC] and [substrates]. Plot of *k*_{obs} vs *I*^{1/2} shows no significant effect of ionic strength on such electron transfer reactions indicating one uncharged species is present at rate determining step.

The effect of dielectric constant of the medium was studied by varying aqueous acetic acid from 30% to 70%. Plot of *k*_{obs} against inverse of dielectric constant (1/*D*) is linear with positive slope suggesting an interaction between positive ion and a dipole¹⁵ at rate determining step.

The reaction mixture was mixed with acrylonitrile and kept for two hours in an inert atmosphere. On dilution with methanol, a white precipitate was formed indicating the intervention of free radicals in the reaction.

Mechanism of the reaction :

Based on the above facts, the probable mechanism may be delineated as in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

where *k*₁ and *k*₂ are different rate constants.

Cr^{III} is the [Cr(H₂O)₆]³⁺ species in aqueous acidic medium.

On basis of this scheme, rate law can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k_1[\text{C}_1]_c + k_2[\text{C}_1]_c[\text{H}^+]^2 \\ &= k_1K[\text{MCC}]_c[\text{RSCH}_3] + \\ &\quad k_2K[\text{MCC}]_c[\text{RSCH}_3]_c[\text{H}^+]^2 \\ &= K[\text{MCC}]_c[\text{RSCH}_3]\{k_1 + k_2[\text{H}^+]^2\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{MCC}]_T &= [\text{MCC}]_c + [\text{C}_1]_c \\ &= [\text{MCC}]_c + K[\text{RSCH}_3]_c[\text{MCC}]_c \\ &= [\text{MCC}]_c(1 + K[\text{RSCH}_3]_c) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{MCC}]_c &= [\text{MCC}]_T / (1 + K[\text{RSCH}_3]_c) \\ \text{Rate} &= \frac{K[\text{RSCH}_3]_c[\text{MCC}]_T\{k_1 + k_2[\text{H}^+]^2\}}{1 + K[\text{RSCH}_3]_c} \end{aligned}$$

If *K*[RSCH₃]_c >> 1

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K[\text{RSCH}_3]_c\{k_1 + k_2[\text{H}^+]^2\}}{K[\text{RSCH}_3]_c}$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2[\text{H}^+]^2$$

Plot of *k*_{obs} vs [H⁺]² gave a good straight line (Fig. 2(a,b)) at constant [amino acid]_T and temperature, which is consistent with the above mechanism. The rate constants *k*₁ and *k*₂ are obtained from plots of *k*_{obs} vs [H⁺]². The value of *k*₁, *k*₂ at different temperatures and their activation parameters are tabulated in Table 2.

Several others cited experimental evidences of formation of intermediate Cr^{IV} in this reaction, dilution of Cr^{IV} by HClO₄ will produce Cr^{VI}. Addition of 0.02 mol dm⁻³ Cr^{III} had no effect on the rate of the reaction. This would suggest that the oxidant in this reaction is not involved after the rate determining steps. Rather a disproportion reaction of Cr^{IV} is assumed to take place followed by a two electron reduction of the Cr^V produced to give the final products Cr^{III} and methionine sulfoxide. A similar observation was made by Haight and his coworkers¹⁶ in the oxidation of hydrazine by Cr^{VI}.

It is interesting to note that reduction by methionine is slower than the corresponding cysteine under the same experimental condition. This is consistent with the postulate¹⁶ that the formation of an intermediate complex is a

Fig. 2(a). Plot of $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[H^+]^2$ for L-cysteine oxidation at 293 K. [L-Cysteine] = (1) $2 \times 10^{-3} M$, (2) $3 \times 10^{-3} M$, (3) $4 \times 10^{-3} M$, (4) $5 \times 10^{-3} M$, (5) $6 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Fig. 2(b). Plot of $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[H^+]^2$ for DL-methionine oxidation at 293 K. [DL-Methionine] = (1) $2 \times 10^{-3} M$, (2) $3 \times 10^{-3} M$, (3) $4 \times 10^{-3} M$, (4) $5 \times 10^{-3} M$, (5) $6 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Table 2. Rate constants k_1 and k_2 for the reaction of MCC with L-cysteine and DL-methionine at different temperature and their activation parameters

Temp. (K)	$10^4 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)		$10^3 k_2$ (mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	
	L-Cysteine	DL-Methionine	L-Cysteine	DL-Methionine
293	5.20	2.96	16.60	9.02
298	10.40	5.60	17.80	20.20
303	12.20	6.98	19.03	29.28
308	20.00	10.24	31.43	40.02
313	24.60	14.20	32.75	51.24
ΔH_1^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	44.82 ± 9.1	54.11 ± 7.1		
ΔH_2^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	26.69 ± 9.0	60.64 ± 12.24		
ΔS_1^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-243.05 ± 29.8	-268.29 ± 23.4		
ΔS_2^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-206.62 ± 30.3	-319.83 ± 40.43		

prerequisite for these redox process. It supports the reports by Mc. Auly and his coworkers¹⁷⁻¹⁹ that the site most susceptible to attack by Cr^{VI} in these substrate is sulfur. The presence of an alkyl group at the site appears to inhibit but not totally prevent the coordination of sulfur to the chromium center. The oxidation of methionine is assumed to take place through the formation of a sulfur bonded (C-S) intermediate complex which undergoes hydrolysis after the electron transfer to give Cr^{III} and methionine sulfoxide as the product which is similar to other reports¹⁷⁻¹⁹ whereas oxidation of cysteine dimerises to cystine as reported by others²⁰⁻²². The decomposition of the sulfur bonded intermediate complex is assumed to be the rate determining step in these reactions.

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